

TOTAL PARACOMPACTNESS AND BANACH SPACES

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we study some problems related to the Corson theorem. In particular we prove that c_0 does not fulfil such a theorem; hence this theorem is not valid for all infinite-dimensional Banach spaces. We give also generalizations of Corson's theorem for some infinite-dimensional normed spaces.

A topological space is said to be totally paracompact [5] if every open basis contains a locally finite covering. It is known [4] that "every totally paracompact complete metric space is C -scattered" and "every σ -locally compact paracompact space is totally paracompact". Then, every Banach space is totally paracompact if and only if it is finite dimensional. Thus, every infinite-dimensional Banach space necessarily has an open basis which contains no locally finite covering (i.e. a coarse open basis [3]). We raise the question of how to give an intrinsic description of those infinite-dimensional Banach spaces such that the open basis formed by all open balls is coarse. Corson's theorem is related with this question:

THE CORSON THEOREM [2]. *For any covering $\mathcal{U}$ of a reflexive, infinite-dimensional Banach space B , where $\mathcal{U}$ is formed by bounded, convex sets, there is a point x in B such that each neighborhood of x meets infinitely many elements of $\mathcal{U}$; i.e., $\mathcal{U}$ is not locally finite.*

In this paper, we study some problems related to the Corson theorem. In particular, we shall prove that c_0 does not fulfil such a theorem, hence this theorem is not valid for all infinite-dimensional Banach spaces. We shall give a generalization of the Corson theorem for some infinite-dimensional normed spaces.

THEOREM 1. *For every $r > 0$, there exists an open covering of c_0 , which is locally finite and is formed by balls of radius r .*

PROOF. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{B_1(0)\} \cup \mathcal{U}_+ \cup \mathcal{U}_-$, where

$$\mathcal{U}_+ = \{B_1(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \mid i \in \mathbb{N}, n \in \mathbb{N}, \\ x_k \in \{0\} \cup \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{N}\}, k \in \{1, \dots, i-1\}\},$$

$$\mathcal{U}_- = \{B_1(y_1, \dots, y_{j-1}, -m - \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \mid j \in \mathbb{N}, m \in \mathbb{N}, \\ y_i \in \{0\} \cup \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{N}\}, i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\}\}.$$

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We shall prove that

- (1) $\mathcal{U}$ covers c_0 .
- (2) $\mathcal{U}$ is locally finite in c_0 .

(1) For each $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in c_0$ there is the first natural number n_0 such that $|x_n| < 1$ for every $n \geq n_0$.

If $n_0 = 1$, we have $|x_n| < 1$ for every $n \geq 1$. Then $\|(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}\|_\infty < 1$ and $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in B_1(0) \in \mathcal{U}$.

If $n_0 > 1$, we have that $|x_{n_0-1}| \geq 1$ and

there is $m = E[x_{n_0-1}] \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|m + \frac{1}{2} - x_{n_0-1}| \leq \frac{1}{2} < 1$ for $x_{n_0-1} \geq 1$;

there is $m = E[-x_{n_0-1}] \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|-m - \frac{1}{2} - x_{n_0-1}| \leq \frac{1}{2} < 1$ for $x_{n_0-1} \leq -1$.

(We write $E[x]$ for the "integral part of x ", the largest integer which does not exceed x .)

Let $(y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in c_0$ be such that $y_n = 0$ for every $n \geq n_0$,

$$y_{n_0-1} = \begin{cases} m + \frac{1}{2} & \text{for } x_{n_0-1} \geq 1, \\ -m - \frac{1}{2} & \text{for } x_{n_0-1} \leq -1, \end{cases} \quad \text{for each } n < n_0 - 1,$$

$$y_n = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } |x_n| < 1, \\ E[x_n] + \frac{1}{2} & \text{for } x_n \geq 1, \\ -E[-x_n] - \frac{1}{2} & \text{for } x_n \leq -1. \end{cases}$$

Then $\|(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} - (y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}\|_\infty < 1$ and $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in B_1((y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}) \in \mathcal{U}_+ \cup \mathcal{U}_- \subset \mathcal{U}$.

(2) We shall prove that $\mathcal{U}_+$ is locally finite in c_0 (for $\mathcal{U}_-$ it is analogous) and clearly we shall have that $\mathcal{U}$ is locally finite in c_0 .

If $\mathcal{U}_+$ is not locally finite in c_0 , there exists $(t_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \in c_0$ such that for each $\delta > 0$ there is an infinite family $\mathcal{F}_\delta$, which is contained in $\mathcal{U}_+$ such that $B_\delta((t_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) \cap B \neq \emptyset$ for every $B \in \mathcal{F}_\delta$; then the set

$$C_\delta = \{i \in \mathbb{N} \mid \text{there is } m \in \mathbb{N}, \text{ there are } x_k \in \{0\} \cup \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{N}\} \\ \text{for each } k \in \{1, \dots, i-1\}$$

$$\text{such that } B_1(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \in \mathcal{F}_\delta\}$$

is nonvoid. Let $0 < \delta < \frac{1}{2}$ in the following argument. C_δ can be infinite or finite.

If C_δ is infinite, then $C_\delta \supset \{i_n \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ such that $i_n < i_{n+1}$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then there exist integers such that

$$\{B_1(x_1^n, \dots, x_{i_n-1}^n, m_n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\} \in \mathcal{F}_\delta$$

and for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $(z_k^n)_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \in c_0$ such that

$$(z_k^n)_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \in B_\delta((t_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) \cap B_1(x_1^n, \dots, x_{i_n-1}^n, m_n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots).$$

Thus, from $|z_{i_n}^n - m_n - \frac{1}{2}| < 1$ and $|z_{i_n}^n - t_{i_n}| < \delta$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ it follows that $m_n - \frac{1}{2} < t_{i_n} + \delta$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $m_n \in \mathbb{N}$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have that $t_{i_n} > \frac{1}{2} - \delta$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $(t_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is not an element of c_0 and this is a contradiction.

If C_δ is finite, let an $i_\delta \in C_\delta$. Then

$$B_\delta((t_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) \cap B_1(x_1, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \neq \emptyset$$

for infinites $(x_1, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2})$, where $x_k \in \{0\} \cup \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{N}\}$ for each $k \in \{1, \dots, i_\delta - 1\}$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, there exists an infinite family $\mathcal{E}_\delta \subset \mathcal{F}_\delta$

formed by balls $B_1(x_1^n, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}^n, m_n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots)$ which, we suppose, are pairwise different.

Now, for i_δ let $U(2, i_\delta - 1)$ be the set of all $(i_\delta - 1)$ -samples with repetitions of the elements 0 and 1.

For each $s \in U(2, i_\delta - 1)$, let $c_s = \{k \in \{1, \dots, i_\delta - 1\} | s(k) \neq 0\}$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \{B_1(x_1, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) | m \in \mathbf{N}, x_k \in \{0\} \cup \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} | p, q \in \mathbf{N}\} \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{for each } k \in \{1, \dots, i_\delta - 1\}\} \\ &= \bigcup_{s \in U(2, i_\delta - 1)} \{B_1(x_1, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) | m \in \mathbf{N}, \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad x_k \in \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} | p, q \in \mathbf{N}\} \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{for each } k \in c_s \text{ and } x_k = 0 \text{ for } k \notin c_s\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $U(2, i_\delta - 1)$ is finite and $\mathcal{S}_\delta$ is infinite, there exists $s_0 \in U(2, i_\delta - 1)$ and an infinite family $\mathcal{A}_\delta \subset \mathcal{S}_\delta$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_\delta &= \{B_1(x_1^n, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}^n, m_n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) | n \in \mathbf{N}, \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad x_k^n = 0 \text{ iff } s_0(k) = 0, \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad x_k^n \in \{p + \frac{1}{2}, -q - \frac{1}{2} | p, q \in \mathbf{N}\} \text{ iff } s_0(k) \neq 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

For every $k \in c_{s_0}$ let

$$S_k = \{x_k^n | \text{some } B_1(y_1, \dots, y_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \in \mathcal{A}_\delta \text{ with } y_k = x_k^n\}$$

and let

$$S_{i_\delta} = \{m + \frac{1}{2} | m \in \mathbf{N} \text{ and some } B_1(y_1, \dots, y_{i_\delta-1}, m + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots) \in \mathcal{A}_\delta\}.$$

Since $\text{card } \mathcal{A}_\delta \leq (\prod_{k \in c_{s_0}} \text{card } S_k) \cdot \text{card } S_{i_\delta}$ and $\mathcal{A}_\delta$ is infinite, there exists $k_0 \in c_{s_0}$ such that S_{k_0} is infinite or S_{i_δ} is infinite.

Suppose S_{i_δ} infinite. Then for each $n \in \mathbf{N}$ there is $(w_k^n)_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \in c_0$ such that

$$(w_k^n)_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \in B_\delta((t_k)_{k \in \mathbf{N}}) \cap B_1(x_1^n, \dots, x_{i_\delta-1}^n, m_n + \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots).$$

Thus, from $|w_{i_\delta}^n - t_{i_\delta}| < \delta$ and $|m_n + \frac{1}{2} - w_{i_\delta}^n| < 1$ for every $n \in \mathbf{N}$ it follows that $m_n + \frac{1}{2} \in (t_{i_\delta} - \frac{3}{2}, t_{i_\delta} + \frac{3}{2})$ for every $n \in \mathbf{N}$. This contradicts the assumption that S_{i_δ} is infinite. Analogously if S_{k_0} is infinite for some $k_0 \in \{1, \dots, i_\delta - 1\}$.

Whence, from the assumption that $\mathcal{U}_+$ is not locally finite in c_0 we have an infinite subfamily $\mathcal{F}_\delta$ of $\mathcal{U}_+$ which allow us to define a nonvoid set C_δ which is neither finite nor infinite.

In the covering $\mathcal{U}$ we can attain the constant radius of the balls to be an arbitrary number $r > 0$, because $rB_1(a) = B_r(ra)$ and the homotheties in a Banach space are homeomorphisms.

PROPOSITION 1. *Let E be a normed space, and F be a subspace of E . If E has a locally finite covering by bounded, convex sets, then also there is a locally finite covering of F by bounded, convex sets.*

PROOF. Let $\mathcal{U}$ be a locally finite covering of E by bounded convex sets. Then $\mathcal{V} = \{U \cap F / U \in \mathcal{U}, U \cap F \neq \emptyset\}$ is also a locally finite covering of F by bounded, convex sets.

REMARK. From the last proposition, Theorem 1, and the Corson theorem it follows that c_0 does not have reflexive, infinite-dimensional Banach subspaces. (This is known; see [1, p. 194].)

THEOREM 2. *Let E be an infinite-dimensional normed space.*

(1) *If there exists a topology T on E such that (E, T) is a T_2 topological vector space and $\bar{B}_1(0)$ is compact in (E, T) , then there is no covering of E , locally finite in the topology defined by the norm, formed by balls.*

(2) *If there exists a topology T on E such that the closed balls of E are closed in (E, T) and $\bar{B}_1(0)$ is compact in (E, T) , then there is no covering of E , locally finite in the topology defined by the norm, formed by balls.*

(3) *If there exists a topology T on E such that (E, T) is T_2 and for each open, bounded, convex subset of E its closure in the topology defined by the norm, is compact in (E, T) , then there is no covering of E , locally finite in the topology defined by the norm, formed by bounded, convex sets.*

(REMARK. (3) generalizes the Corson theorem.)

PROOF. It is analogous to the proof of the Corson theorem [2].

COROLLARY. *If an infinite-dimensional Banach space B is conjugate, then there is no locally finite covering of B by balls.*

PROOF. It follows from (1) of Theorem 2 and from the Dixmier-Goldberg-Ruston Theorem [6].

REMARK. Theorem 1 contradicts A. Pełczyński's note [9]: "It verifies the result analogous to Corson's theorem for any Banach space in which there is a weakly closed cone, every closed convex and bounded part of which is weakly compact. Such a cone exists in every Banach space in which there is a weakly convergent sequence which is not norm-convergent." Nevertheless, this idea allows us to give a new generalization of the Corson theorem.

THEOREM 3. *Let E be an infinite-dimensional normed space. If there exists a topology T on E such that (E, T) is T_2 and there is a cone K in E , with nonvoid interior in E and such that for every open bounded convex subset of E its closure in the topology defined by the norm on E , relativized to K , is compact in (E, T) , then there is no covering of E , locally finite in the topology defined by the norm, formed by bounded, convex sets.*

PROOF. The result follows by an argument analogous to the proof of the Corson theorem.

OPEN PROBLEMS.

Problem 1. Give a characterization of those infinite-dimensional normed spaces such that the open basis formed by all open balls is coarse.

Problem 2. Give an intrinsic description of those infinite-dimensional normed spaces E which have a topology T such that (E, T) is a T_2 topological vector space and $\bar{B}_1(0)$ is compact in (E, T) .

Problem 3. Give a characterization of those infinite-dimensional normed spaces such that the open basis formed by all open, bounded, convex subsets is coarse.

Problem 4. Does the Banach space $c_0(A)$, for an arbitrary index set A , admit a locally finite covering by open balls?

Problem 5. Does the James Hagler space [J. Hagler, *A counterexample to several questions about Banach spaces*, *Studia Math.* **60** (1977), 289–308] admit a locally finite covering by open balls?

(Problems 4 and 5 were raised by the referee.)

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